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THE JOURNAL OF WEST AFRICAN LANGUAGES

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EDITORIAL NOTE

This issue is a little different from previous issues. Since a number of articles which deal with historical, comparative and classificatory questions are ready for publication, it seemed useful to publish them together in the same issue rather than intersperse them with descriptive or sociolinguistic articles.

The issue is also a little longer than usual as special funds were made available to include the substantial data that Professor Armstrong has collected on the Idoma group of languages. This Journal welcomes articles which include substantial language data.

The first two articles in the issue are closely related. When Dr. Capo submitted his article, with his agreement Dr. Stewart was invited to comment upon it. I would like to see more scholarly interchange of this sort in future issues of the Journal. Any offers?

The October issue returns to more descriptive matters. The whole issue focuses on a common topic - locative constructions. All the articles will deal with this feature. Readers' reactions to devoting issues to a common topic of this sort are invited. Let us hear from you.

Now that the Journal is back on a regular publication basis it seems useful to include a "Notices" section. Details of projects, conferences, etc. likely to be of interest to readers of J.W.A.L. are invited. They should be sent to the Editor.

THE VOWELS OF PROTO-ĒDOID

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Ten oral vowels are reconstructed for Proto-Ēdoïd (PE). It is also assumed that PE operated vowel harmony of the Kwa type in which one set of vowels is characterized by an expanded pharynx and the other by an absence of such an expansion.

There is a reduced role for vowel harmony in modern Ēdoïd languages. The reason for this is the reduction of the original ten-vowel system to a nine-, eight, or even seven-vowel system in the Ēdoïd languages.

The ways in which vowel system reduction takes place are discussed: the vowels *ə, *ɪ, and *ɔ are the first to go in that order. The origin of vowel sequences is also discussed: in CVCV stems, the second consonant, -C₂- was invariably a lenis one, while the final vowel, -V₂, was -i/-ɪ, or -u/-ɔ or -ə/-a. The loss of -C₂- created vowel sequences.

Finally, nasals and nasalization are examined as they affect the reconstruction of the PE vowel system. In particular, the question is raised whether PE had significant vowel nasalization. The conclusion is that there was and that -C₂-nasals of PE are derived from their oral counterparts by a nasal rule.

On est arrivé à la conclusion que le proto-édoïde (PE), devait posséder dix voyelles orales, et il est également admis que le processus d'harmonie vocalique du PE était du type de celui du groupe kwa, dans lequel l'un des groupes de voyelles est caractérisé par une dilatation du pharynx et l'autre par une absence de dilatation du pharynx.

Le processus d'harmonie vocalique a une fonction plus restreinte dans les langues édoïdes modernes, en effet, il y a dans ces langues diminution du système original à dix voyelles, à des systèmes à neuf, huit ou même sept voyelles.

La façon dont ces diminutions du nombre de voyelles dans les systèmes vocaliques apparaissent, est étudiée dans l'article que nous résumons. Les premières voyelles à disparaître sont dans l'ordre [*ə], [*ɪ], [*ɔ]. L'origine des séquences vocaliques est également étudiée dans cet article. Dans la

structure CVCV, la deuxième consonne $-C_2-$, était invariablement une consonne faible et la voyelle $-V_2-$ était toujours $-i/[ɪ]$, ou $-u/[*ɔ]$ ou encore $-[ə]/a-$. Lors de la disparition de la consonne $-C_2-$ une séquence vocalique apparaissait donc.

Enfin, l'article étudie les nasales et la nasalisation pour, par ce biais, retrouver le système vocalique du PE. La question se pose, en particulier de savoir s'il y avait un phénomène de nasalisation des voyelles du proto-édoïde. La réponse est affirmative, et d'autre part les consonnes $-C_2-$ nasales du proto-édoïde, dériveraient des consonnes orales équivalentes suivant une règle spécifique.

0. INTRODUCTION

The Èdoid languages are traditionally classified as Kwa (Greenberg 1963). More recently, Bennett and Sterk (1977) have classified them as a group (?) within Eastern South-Central Niger-Congo. Geographically, they are found mostly in the Bendel State of Nigeria. Delta-Èdoid (DE) languages are spoken in the Rivers State while some North-Central (NCE) and North-Western (NWE) Èdoid languages are spoken in the Bendel/Ondo border areas of Ondo State.

1. THE VOWELS OF PROTO-ÈDOID (PE)

Ten oral vowels are reconstructed for Proto-Èdoid:

- (1)
- | | |
|---|---|
| i | u |
| ɪ | ɔ |
| e | o |
| ɛ | ɔ |
| ə | |
| a | |

Donwa (forthcoming) has done a spectrographic investigation of vowels in Isoko and discovered that \underline{i} and \underline{o} are in fact lower than \underline{e} and $\underline{ɔ}$. If this were the situation in PE, it could mean that the non-expanded vowels were lower all round than their expanded counterparts (see below). Synchronic evidence from modern Èdoid languages suggests that PE operated a vowel harmony rule. This suggestion is confirmed by the pattern of vowel distribution in our reconstructed PE lexicon.

We assume that vowel harmony in PE was of the Kwa type in which vowels fall into two sets, one characterized by an expanded pharynx and the other by the absence of such an expansion. The two harmony sets in PE would thus be as in (2):

(2)	EXPANDED PHARYNX		NON-EXPANDED PHARYNX	
	i	u	ɪ	ɔ
	e	o	ɛ	ɔ
	ə		a	

According to the vowel harmony rule, all affix vowels had to agree with stem vowels in pharynx width. In the case of polysyllabic stems, all vowels also had to agree in terms of pharynx width.

In the modern Eḍoid languages, there is a reduced role for vowel harmony. It is observed that the fewer the vowels in a given system, the less the role of vowel harmony. Thus vowel harmony is virtually non-existent in the NCE languages (Eḍo, Auchi, Ghotuḍ, etc.) where the original ten-vowel system has been reduced to seven. In Delta-Eḍoid, where ten-vowel systems still exist, vowel harmony is at its most symmetrical and rigid. The NWE and the SWE situations are intermediate between these two (DE and NCE) extremes.

2. VOWEL SYSTEM REDUCTION

The implication of postulating a ten-vowel system for PE is that most Eḍoid languages have reduced the original system in various ways. The first step is, of course, to prove that we are dealing with reduction rather than expansion in the Eḍoid situation.

The evidence for postulating reduction is overwhelming and conclusive: while *i and *e have regular i- and e- reflexes respectively, *ɪ shifts to i, ɪ, e, or ɛ! Similarly, while *u and *o have u- and o- reflexes respectively, *ɔ has u-, ɔ-, o- and ɔ- reflexes. These observations are parallel to what happens in the case of *ə and *a. *ə has a very varied set of reflexes but *a does not. All these observations are supported by the evidence in Table 1.

Some generalizations may be drawn from the way in which the original ten-vowel system has been reduced in the Eḍoid languages: (See Table 1 overleaf.)

- (3) a. In the nine-vowel system, there is no /ə/.
- b. In the eight-vowel system, there is no /ə/ and no /ɪ/.
- c. In the seven-vowel system, there are no /ə, ɪ, ɔ/.

An example of (3a) in Eḡeḡe (Engenni). Ibilo (NWE) is an example of (3b) while all NCE languages provide examples of (3c). In cases of (3a), [ə] sometimes remains as an allophone of /a/ while, in cases of (3b), there is no trace of [ə] but [ɪ] is an allophone of /i/.

Table 1: Vowel correspondences in Ẹdoid

		i	ɪ	e	ɛ	ə	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
DE:	Degema	i	ɪ	e	ɛ	ə	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
	Egēṅē	i	ɪ	e	ɛ	e	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
	Epie	i	ɪ	e	ɛ		a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
SWE:	Ẹṛụwa	i	ɪ	e	ɛ	ɛ	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
	Isoko	i	ɪ	e	ɛ	^e ɛ	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
	Okpe	i	e	e	ɛ	ɛ	a	ɔ	o	o	
	Urhobo	i	e	e	ɛ	ɛ	a	ɔ	o	o	u
	Uvbię	i	ɪ	e	ɛ	ɛ	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
NCE:	Ẹdo	i	e	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	o	u
	Aoma	i	e	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	o	u
	Avbianwu	i	e	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	o	u
	Auchi	i	e	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	o	u
	Uneme	i	e	e	ɛ	ɔ	a	ɔ	o	o	u
	Ghotuṣ	i	e	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	o	u
NWE:	Q̣ḷṣ̣ma	i	ɛ	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
	Ẹṃhaḷḥē	i	ɛ	e	ɛ		a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
	Ibilo	i	ɛ	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	ɔ	u
	Uhami	i	i	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	ɔ	u	u
	Ẹḥuẹun	i	i	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	u	u
	Ukue	i	i	e	ɛ	a	a	ɔ	o	u	u

In the ten-vowel system of Dɛgɛma, /ə/ is forbidden in prefix position (cf. Elugbe 1976); in the nine-vowel system of Ɛgɛnɛ, /ɪ/ and /o/ are forbidden in prefix position. It would appear that this kind of distributional restriction is one of the first steps in vowel system reduction.

Table 1 and our discussion so far are summarized in (4):

(4) Vowel system reduction routes in Ɛdoid

It may well be that PE *ə was closer and therefore more centralised than here indicated since Table 1 and our summary in (4) show that it has the ability to shift to the greatest variety of vowels. It is followed by *ɪ and *ɔ. The evidence also shows that although Elugbe (1973) did not reconstruct *ə, there is ample evidence for its reconstruction. The inclusion of data from Dɛgɛma (DE) and Unɛmɛ (NCE) has been useful in bringing a new dimension into the correspondences (see the items 'river' and 'two' in the appendix).

If we take Donwa's forthcoming position on Isoko as representative of what may have operated in PE, we should re-arrange the vowels of PE as in (1[~]):

It would become obvious that the three most central vowels are the most prone to change. It may well be that peripheral vowels are more resistant to change than non-peripheral (i.e. central) vowels - at least within vowel systems of the Kwa type with vowel harmony.

3. VOWEL SEQUENCES AND -V₂-

Vowel sequences are widely attested in the Ɛdoid languages. The sequences are either closing or opening. A closing sequence of vowels is one in which the last vowel is closer (i.e. higher on the Height scale) than the first. On the other hand, an opening

sequence is one in which the last vowel is more open (i.e. lower on a Height scale) than the first.

Thus we find opening sequences $-iV$, $-rV$, $-oV$, and $-uV$ in which v is lower than the close \underline{i} , \underline{r} , \underline{o} , \underline{u} . On the other hand typical closing sequences are $-\underline{ei}$, \underline{ai} , $-\underline{ɔɔ}$, \underline{ou} etc.

There are more vowel sequences to be found in a typical modern Eḍoid language than I postulate for PE. This arises from the fact that most Eḍoid languages have zero-reflex for the PE $-C_2-$ consonants which were lenis $-\underline{dh-}$, $-\underline{mh-}$, $-\underline{nh-}$, etc. (see Elugbe 1980 for a discussion of this).

In CVCV stems of PE, there was a restriction as to the vowels which could occur at $-V_2$. Only $*\underline{-i}/*\underline{-r}$, $*\underline{-o}/*\underline{-u}$ and $*\underline{-ə}/*\underline{-a}$ could occur there. Once a $-C_2-$ was lost, original CVCV stems became CVV in which, very often, $-V_2$ was a close vowel. Donwa (forthcoming) gives evidence which shows a development CVCV > CVV > CV within the dialects of Isoko. Elugbe and Williamson (1977) also give evidence from the Eḍoid languages to support the view that some vowel sequences have arisen from the loss of $-C_2-$ in the Eḍoid languages.

4. VOWELS, NASALS, AND NASALIZATION IN PE

In Elugbe (1973) I suggested that significant vowel nasalization was a feature of PE. I also said then that of all the vowels of PE, only $*\underline{e}$ and $*\underline{o}$ had no significantly nasalized counterparts. This point about nasalized $\underline{ẽ}$ and $\underline{õ}$ was based on the observation that no $*\underline{ẽ}$ or $*\underline{õ}$ could be convincingly reconstructed for PE.

Nasalization in the Eḍoid languages is often traceable to PE $-\underline{mh-}$ and $-\underline{nh-}$, i.e. $-C_2-$ nasals, which have been lost. But there are also cases where synchronic nasalization is not traceable to a PE lenis nasal in $-C_2-$ or any other position. It is for such cases that significant nasalization is postulated in the 1973 work, giving us $*\underline{C}\underline{V}$ and $*\underline{C}\underline{V}\underline{V}$ stems. However, in the 1977 work by Elugbe and Williamson, PE $*\underline{C}\underline{V}$ and $*\underline{C}\underline{V}\underline{V}$ are said to have been derived from a pre- or early-Proto-Eḍoid form in which a velar nasal $-C_2-$ occurred. In Elugbe (1980), that position is slightly modified and $-N-$ is postulated in place of $-\eta-$. Thus the item 'tree' is reconstructed at various stages as in (5):

(5)	1973	PE $*\underline{o}$ - $\underline{thãĩ}$	'tree'
	1977	$*\underline{o}$ - $\underline{thãŋr}$	
	1980	$*\underline{o}$ - $\underline{thãNr}$	

The difference between the 1977 and the 1980 positions is that $-\eta-$ was postulated for a pre-Proto-Eḍoid level while $-N-$ is postulated

for PE. There is also no claim in the 1980 work that -N- was necessarily -ŋ-. In fact, the claim is that -N- may never have been realized segmentally but rather as nasalization of the surrounding vowels.

In making a case for a pre-PE -ŋ-, Elugbe and Williamson (1977) point to two considerations which are relevant: (1) the irregularity of having -mh- and -nh- but not -ŋ- (our -N-); and (2) the derivation of significant nasalization from the loss of -mh- and -nh-.

The case, already made in 1977 against the background of Benue-Kwa, will be briefly amplified here. If we assume that the typical PE stem was CVCV (and occasionally CV, CVV or CVC) in which -C₂- was frequently a lenis nasal -mh-, -nh-, or -N-, we find that all Eḍoid languages have lost -N-, with faint traces of it left in the form of vowel nasalization; on the other hand, -mh- and -nh- are retained here and there. Using Dẹgema and Egeḅe (DE), Isoko (SWE), Aoma (NCE), and Ibilo (NWE) as examples, we find the following interesting situation:

(6)	Proto-Eḍoid	CVmhV	CVnhV	CVNV
>	Dẹgema	CVm	CVn	CṼV/CVV
>	Egeḅe	CVm(V)	CVn(V)	CVV
>	Isoko	CVV	CVrV	CVV
>	Aoma	CVmV	CṼ	CṼ
>	Ibilo	CV	CVŋV	CV

The languages in (6) are not representative of what happens within each sub-group of Eḍoid. For example, the Isoko examples obscure the fact that PE -mh- has a -m-reflex in Okpẹ, another SWE language. What (6) does is give us an idea of the variety of processes by which vowel nasalization and stem reduction have taken place in Eḍoid. (7) is a practical demonstration of (6):

(7)	PE: E-nhamhɪ	khɔnhɪ	U-thanhɪ	dhɪ-kɪnɛ
De.	è-nám	kɔn	ó-!táí	ú-!kíé
Eg.	à-nàm(ò)	kɔn(ɪ)	è-tàɪ	í-kìè
Is.	à-ràò	hɔrɪ	ú-ré	é-ké
Ao.	é-ámì	xòí	ó-rà	é-kè
Ib.	à-ḅà	khɔḅɔ	ú-ḅà	ḅá-cà
Eng.	'meat'	'fight'	'tree'	'egg'

What is clear from (7) is that the most unpopular -C₂- is -N-. Beyond that some languages have dropped -nh- while retaining -mh- (e.g. Aoma); others have dropped -mh- while retaining -nh- (e.g. Ibilo).

1. Proto-Edoid <u>*-ki</u> 'market'			3. Proto-Edoid <u>*deNi</u> 'fall'			5. Proto-Edoid <u>*E-da i-</u> 'river'		
DE:	Degema	è-kí ì-	DE:	Degema	deĩ	DE:	Degema	édè í-
	Egēne	è-kì		Egēne	dei		Egēne	é-dè
	Epie	e-ki		Epie	deĩ		Epie	é-dè
SWE:	Eruwa	è-kí ì-	SWE:	Eruwa	ze	SWE:	Eruwa	í-sè
	Isoko	è-kì		Isoko	tʃe < tie		Isoko	é-tè (í-)
	Okpe	é-yì		Okpe	se		Okpe	(ù-ríé)
	Urhobo	è-kì		Urhobo	ʃe		Urhobo	(ò-ríé)
	Uvbie	è-kì		Uvbie	rie		Uvbie	(ù-ríè)
NCE:	Edo	è-kì	NCE:	Edo	de	NCE:	Edo	è-zè
	Aoma	è-kì		Aoma	de		Aoma	é-dè
	Auchi	à-kì ì-		Auchi	de		Auchi	é-dà é-
	Avbianwu	à-kì		Avbianwu	de		Avbianwu	é-dà é-
	Uneme	à-kì		Uneme	de		Uneme	é-dò
	Ghotuo	ghò-kì		Ghotuo	de		Ghotuo	ēdā ē-
NWE:	Oloṃa	ghè-kì	NWE:	Oloṃa	ze	NWE:	Oloṃa	-
	Emhalhe	wè-kì rù-kì		Emhalhe	ze		Emhalhe	(ó-kè)
	Ibilo	è-cì		Ibilo	dze		Ibilo	(ó-kphò)
	Uhami	è-cì		Uhami	ze		Uhami	(ú-kò)
	Ehueun	è-hi		Ehueun	ze		Ehueun	(ó-kè)
	Ukue	è-kì		Ukue	de		Ukue	(ù-kòu)
2. Proto-Edoid <u>*dhr</u> 'eat'			4. Proto-Edoid <u>*dē</u> 'buy'			6. Proto-Edoid <u>*i-və</u> 'two'		
DE:	Degema	dɪ	DE:	Degema	dē	DE:	Degema	i-və
	Egēne	dɪ		Egēne	(do)		Egēne	í-vè
	Epie	dɪ		Epie	dē		Epie	í-vè
SWE:	Eruwa	rɪ [ɹɪ]	SWE:	Eruwa	dē	SWE:	Eruwa	í-vè
	Isoko	rɪ		Isoko	dē		Isoko	í-vè
	Okpe	rɛ		Okpe	dē		Okpe	é-và
	Urhobo	lɛ		Urhobo	dē		Urhobo	í-vè
	Uvbie	rɪ		Uvbie	dē		Uvbie	í-vè
NCE:	Edo	lɛ/ɹɛ	NCE:	Edo	dē	NCE:	Edo	è-vá
	Aoma	e		Aoma	dē		Aoma	è-vá
	Auchi	lɛ		Auchi	dē		Auchi	è-vá
	Avbianwu	lɛ		Avbianwu	dē		Avbianwu	è-vá
	Uneme	lɛ		Uneme	dē		Uneme	è-vá
	Ghotuo	e		Ghotuo	dē		Ghotuo	è-vā
NWE:	Oloṃa	rɛ	NWE:	Oloṃa	dē	NWE:	Oloṃa	é-wá ?
	Emhalhe	rɛ		Emhalhe	dē		Emhalhe	è-vá
	Ibilo	rɛ		Ibilo	dē		Ibilo	è-vá
	Uhami	ri		Uhami	dē		Uhami	è-vá
	Ehueun	ri		Ehueun	dē		Ehueun	è-vā
	Ukue	dɪ		Ukue	dē		Ukue	è-vá

7. Proto-Edoid *ma
'mould'

DE: Dẹgẹma (dum)
Egẹne ma
Epie ma

SWE: Eruwa ma
Isoko ma
Okpe ma
Urhobo ma
Uvbie ma

NCE: Edo ma
Aoma ma
Auchi ma
Avbianwu ma
Uneme ma
Ghotuo ma

NWE: Oloṃa ma
Emhalhe ma
Ibilo ma
Uhami ma
Ehueun ma
Ukue ma

9. Proto-Edoid *do
'steal'

DE: Dẹgẹma do
Egẹne do
Epie dō

SWE: Eruwa so
Isoko to
Okpe so
Urhobo co
Uvbie co

NCE: Edo (rhaa)
Aoma do
Auchi (tue)
Avbianwu (tue)
Uneme do, do(ɔ)
Ghotuo do

NWE: Oloṃa zo
Emhalhe zo
Ibilo dzo
Uhami zo
Ehueun zo
Ukue do

11. Proto-Edoid *fumhi
'swell'

DE: Dẹgẹma fu (TW)
Egẹne fuo
Epie fue (TW)

SWE: Eruwa fi(ri)
Isoko fu
Okpe fu
Urhobo (vbo [vɔ])
Uvbie fu(ru)

NCE: Edo hiv iã [hiã]
Aoma humu
Auchi fumhi
Avbianwu fumhi
Uneme fumhu
Ghotuo humhi

NWE: Oloṃa -
Emhalhe (bie)
Ibilo (bio)
Uhami (mina)
Ehueun (zo)
Ukue (dho)

3. Proto-Edoid *ghU-bɔ
A- 'arm, hand'

DE: Dẹgẹma ɔ-bɔ à-
Egẹne ɔ-bɔ
Epie ɔ-bɔ

SWE: Eruwa à-bɔ
Isoko ɔ-bɔ à-
Okpe ɔ-bɔ à-
Urhobo ɔ-bɔ à-
Uvbie à-bɔ

NCE: Edo ɔ-bɔ
Aoma ɔ-bɔ
Auchi ɔ-bɔ a-
Avbianwu ɔ-bɔ a-
Uneme ɔ-bɔ a-
Ghotuo ghɔ-bɔ a-

NWE: Oloṃa ghɔ-bɔ á-
Emhalhe wɔ-bɔ á-
Ibilo ɔ-bɔ á-
Uhami ɔ-bɔ
Ehueun ɔ-wɔ
Ukue ɔ-bɔ

10. Proto-Edoid *0-bɔ
A- 'doctor'

DE: Dẹgẹma ɔ-bɔ é-
Egẹne ɔ-bɔ
Epie ɔ-bɔ

SWE: Eruwa ɔ-bɔ í-
Isoko ɔ-bɔ í-
Okpe ɔ-bɔ
Urhobo ɔ-bo é-
Uvbie à-bɔ

NCE: Edo ɔ-bɔ
Aoma ɔ-bɔ
Auchi ɔ-bɔ é-
Avbianwu ɔ-bɔ é-
Uneme ɔ-bɔ í-
Ghotuo ɔ-bɔ é-

NWE: Oloṃa á-bɔ
Emhalhe ɔ-bɔ é-
Ibilo ɔ-bo é-
Uhami ɔ-bɔ
Ehueun ɔ-bɔ
Ukue ɔ-bu

12. Proto-Edoid *vie
'cry, weep'

DE: Dẹgẹma vie
Egẹne vie
Epie -

SWE: Eruwa vie
Isoko vie
Okpe vie
Urhobo vie
Uvbie vie

NCE: Edo vie
Aoma vie
Auchi vie
Avbianwu vie
Uneme vie
Ghotuo vie

NWE: Oloṃa vie
Emhalhe vie
Ibilo vie
Uhami vie
Ehueun vie
Ukue vie

13. Proto-Edoid *ghu -chɔGi A- 'ear'		14. Proto-Edoid * U-bhaGI/* U-baGr 'house, room'	
DE: Dɛgɛma	ó-s̄ṓ á-	DE: Dɛgɛma	ó-vāī [óβāī]
Egɛnɛ	é-s̄ò	Egɛnɛ	-
Epiɛ	í-s̄ó̄	Epiɛ	-
SWE: Eɾɿwa	(í-yó) (noun derived from yō 'hear')	SWE: Eɾɿwa	ò-wá ɿ-
Isoko	ó-z̄ó f-	Isoko	-
Okpɛ	ò-rh̄ó [òró] è-	Okpɛ	[òɣwá]
Urhobo	ò-rh̄ó [òró] è-	Urhobo	[u-wěvbī]
Uvbiɛ	è-s̄ó	Uvbiɛ	-
NCE: Edo	è-h̄ó	NCE: Edo	ò-wá
Aoma	é-h̄ò	Aoma	ó-à
Auchi	é-vb̄ò [éúò]	Auchi	ó-vb̄à [óuà]
Avbianwu	é-w̄ò	Avbianwu	ó-vb̄à [óuà] 'room'
Unɛmɛ	é-sh̄ò	Unɛmɛ	ó-vb̄à [óuà]
Ghotuɔ	ghō-h̄òghì [yōh̄òɣì] ē-	Ghotuɔ	ō-vb̄àghì [ōuàɣì]
NWE: Oloṃa	gh̄ó-z̄ò é-	NWE: Oloṃa	(à-fè)
Emhalhɛ	w̄ó-z̄ò é-	Emhalhɛ	-
Ibilo	ó-z̄ò é-	Ibilo	(ú-kpò)
Uhami	é-s̄ò	Uhami	(ò-dé)
Ehɿeun	ē-rh̄ò [ēɿò]	Ehɿeun	(ō-dé)
Ukue	é-rh̄ò [éɿò]	Ukue	(ò-dé)

FOOTNOTES

*This is a slightly modified version of a paper of the same title presented at the 15th West African Languages Congress, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, from 4th-10th April, 1982.

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